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Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia to United Nations

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Keynote

Every law is a matter of common intelligence. Every legal fact, legal incidence, and law can not be registered by the people of the universe. This is a limitation of human being in the planet. Legal incidences, occurrences, and situations are the prerequisite of the proposal of any law. Therefore, every registered law is a registered symbol to continue the legal practice of lawyers, justices, researchers, and human rights practitioners to continue university policy, country policy, and the policy of United Nations (UN) for surviving in the planet. Therefore, every human rights commission should

- understand the word meaning of human rights in English.
- understand the responsibilities and duties of human rights commission.
- understand the legal duties of human rights commission for the people for the country for the UN.

Outcomes and proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia

1. Every human rights commission should have a legal voice about any life-threatening conspiracy if there is any limitation or delaying of court hearing in court room.

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2. Every human rights commission should have a legal voice about any international conspiracy if there is any limitation or delaying of court hearing in court room.
3. Every human rights commission should have a legal voice to satisfy the safety of citizen/international scholar if there is any negligence or delaying of court hearing in court room.
4. Every human rights commission should have a legal voice if the citizen/international victim/plaintiff has the fund crisis to establish the legal claim and legal rights in international platform.
5. Every human rights commission should have a legal voice and recommendation to government to the department of legal aids to the department of the attorney general to the authority of high court if the international victim/plaintiff has the fund crisis to establish the legal claim and legal rights in international platform.
6. Every human rights commission should have a legal voice to signify the legal standing of human rights commission, the legal position of human rights commission and the legal decision of human rights commission to the attorney general to the authority of high court to the authority of UN.
7. Every human rights commission should have a judicial board of a government to analyze the national/international crime and the claim of a plaintiff. The fees of expert lawyers/board of justice should be paid by the human rights commission. Therefore, every human rights commission may go to the high court on behalf of plaintiff and/or government and/or third party of the government.
8. Every human rights commission may recommend and approve the full funding of plaintiff, living and fooding to plaintiff, judicial costs to plaintiff until the final decision or order of the high court of Australia; if the human rights commission is also a registered and authorized commission of any government.
9. Every human rights commission should try to establish the duty, the commission should not be afraid to claim to shout to proceed to invest to approve against the criminal and crimes.
10. Every human rights commission should know about their duties and responsibilities to eliminate their penalty due to negligence of the commission.
11. Every human rights commission should have a research and development department and continuous stuff training support to establish their duties of human rights to serve the country to serve the United Nations (UN).
12. A long-term delaying of government limitation should not have the filing requirement of number of page limitations to enhance the legal responsibilities of any government.
13. Human rights commission of Australia or international human rights commission or UN may expel/suspend the administrative service, the political party, and the government

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 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
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authority of a central government of a country if the government can not establish/display the legal rights of student/professor/researcher/victim. Accordingly, human rights commission of UN may implement/extend the duty if the UN is also an organization if UN is displaying the organization.

14. Every president/chairman should have expertise to ensure the service to the commission to the country to the government without which the designated post should be invalid.
15. Every president/chairman should have a time to read to assess the complaint letter of the citizen/government to ensure the service to the commission to the country to the government without which the designated post should be invalid.
16. Every president/chairman should have a capability to understand to assess the complaint letter of the citizen/government scholar to ensure the service to the commission to the country to the government without which the designated post should be invalid.
17. Any negligence of any registered commission/president of any country should be punishable offence of 1,00,000 Australian penalty units.
18. Human rights commission of Australia should ensure the safety, food and living cost support for the citizen/PhD scholar/government scholar during the crisis moment and/or the moment of the criminal attack and/or the moment of life-threatening conspiracy and/or the moment of judicial assessment.
19. Human rights commission of UN should ensure the safety, food and living cost support for the citizen/PhD scholar/government scholar during the crisis moment and/or the moment of the criminal attack and/or the moment of life-threatening conspiracy and/or the moment of judicial assessment.
20. Every country should have free of cost legal support for the PhD scholar if the PhD scholar has zero income in Australia and/or any country of political party and/or non-political party.
21. Every human rights commission should serve like the word meaning of human rights without which the display of human rights commission should be stopped globally without which the word of human rights should be replaced.
22. Salary is proportional to the designation of the organization of a country. Responsibility is also proportional to the designation of the organization of a country. Penalty is also proportional to the designation of the organization of a country. Punishment is also proportional to the designation of the organization of a country. Hence, zero responsibility of a top administrative person tend to the death penalty and/or higher penalty units. Therefore, the symptom of zero responsibility in public service is also a crime of death penalty.

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23. Every citizen/government scholar has right to claim against any government if there is a symptom of high-risk crime if there is high-risk misconduct in higher education and public service. Human rights commission, attorney general, high court, and government legal aids are the core assessor of the country are the non-political assessor of the country to solve the critical legal issue to approve the legal fund to approve the legal stipend to eliminate the crime of a country of a government.
24. Every government officer or relevant officer or minister or president or relevant commission should read should assess the full pages of the relevant claim of the citizen/government scholar to eliminate the crime of a country of a government.
25. Every government is an organization is a surviving technique in the planet. Under the valid circumstances, a professor/government scholar may order to the government authority to approve the fund to eliminate any special crime of the country of the government under the special act/support of the government and/or United Nations.
26. Under the valid circumstances, a professor/government scholar may order to the government authority to approve the fund to do any specific research of the country of the government under the special act of the government and/or United Nations.
27. In valid circumstances, every president of human rights commission may order to the government to approve the legal fund to eliminate the criminals and crimes of the government of the country.
28. Every non-qualified person should not continue any job in public service/commission to eliminate/ignore the self-liability and self-responsibility to overcome the penalty and punishment.

Keywords

Human Rights, Human Rights Commission, RMIT, Legal Acts, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Mr. Hugh de Kretser

1 Letter of proceeding

Date: 24 October 2025

Mr. Hugh de Kretser, President
Human Rights Commission, The Commonwealth of Australia

Mr./Ms. Kate
Complaint Information Officer
National Information Services (incl Respect@Work)

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1.1 Subject of reporting to Mr. Hugh de Kretser, President, Human Rights Commission, The Commonwealth of Australia

Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia to United Nations

Dear Mr. Hugh de Kretser,

The proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission is being forwarded to Mr. Hugh de Kretser, President, Human Rights Commission, The Commonwealth of Australia to the reading room of Mr. Hugh de Kretser to ensure the administrative order or recommendation to the relevant authority of Australia and/or United Nations. The administrative order or recommendation should be the official duty or routine duty of Mr. Hugh de Kretser if the Human Rights Commission is also a valid organization of the country in Australia. The administrative order or recommendation of president should be the self-protection/legal protection of Mr. Hugh de Kretser if the human rights commission is also a unit of Australian public service.

2 General duties of human rights commission

Elimination of crimes are the core duty of the human rights commission where the human rights is failing where the human rights is declining where the victim is suffering and suffering. The commission should not be the representative of any political organization; the commission should be the representative of any country or UN. Any negligence of any registered commission/president of any country should be punishable offence of 1,00,000 Australian penalty units. Everyone/every authority should assess to approve to sign this punishment?

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Figure 1. General duties of a human rights commission of any country and United Nations.

3 General duties of human rights commission

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4 Legal explanation against legal notice to Mr. Hugh de Kretser, President, Human Rights Commission, The Commonwealth of Australia on 27 September 2025 (Hossain, 2025a)

4.1 Root crime/source crime/force crime/slavery crime in Australia, but the zero responsibility of Australian human rights commission and the government of Australia and the United Nations (UN)

Figure 2, how should the legal responsibilities of Australian human rights commission be 0% to fight against international criminal since 2022-2023? What should be the official duty of a president at human rights commission? Mr. Hugh de Kretser should satisfy to the Australian community to the global community to the UN. Without which, these are the crime of death penalty of a president if the president can not assess the life-threatening conspiracy can not ensure the legal support can not approve the legal fund. Nobody should deny the responsibility. There is no chance to deny the responsibility if the president is trading his name as the president of the Australian human rights commission. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain invested and wrote thousand and thousand hours, but the human rights commission had/has no time to read to assess for the peace surviving in the planet. Figure 1, 2; possibly, Mr. Hugh de Kretser, President, Human Rights Commission, The Commonwealth of Australia is a paid official of Australia, but Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a non-paid official of Australia to assess and claim the life-threatening conspiracy. Hence, the graphical comparison in figure 2 shows that the legal responsibilities of life-threatening conspiracy of Mr. Hugh de Kretser, President, Australian human rights commission is 0% when the legal responsibilities of life-threatening conspiracy of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is almost 100% when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is getting zero fund of Australia. What should be the responsibilities of Australian human rights commission if the commission can not assess, if the commission can not support to the victim, if the commission can not debate to ensure the legal support and legal fund? These are the symptom of supporting the root crime in Australia, and wasting time of victim and plaintiff under the organized platform of a country of a government of UN. These are the playing symptom with the victim and plaintiff. These are the joking symptom with the victim and plaintiff in Australia. These are the symptom of artificial harassment, official ceasing, artificial bullet, and automatic threat to the victim and plaintiff. Where is the human rights? Who should take care the situation? Where is the support of peace surviving in the planet? If there is no human rights, what is the necessity to keep to display the office of human rights commission? Why should Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain write letter to the commission. It should be wrong and crime to confuse the people in the name of human rights commission if there is zero service of human rights commission. It should be wrong and crime to confuse the people in the name of human rights commission if the

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human rights commission can not assess the full claim of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain if the human rights commission can not assess the full pages of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. It is not possible to make any shorter version without approving the senior professor category funding to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain when he is making the shorter version and individual version since 2021-2022 when he is explaining briefly to satisfy the punishment to the international criminals. No assessor should count the page numbers to protect the violence in the country, every reviewer should read the whole pages of letters to satisfy the punishment to the international criminals (M. A. Hossain, 2023bx).

Figure 2. Comparison of legal responsibilities of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian public service since 2022-2023 (M. A. Hossain, 2023bx; M. A. Hossain, 2023e).

4.2 Australian human rights commission should pay the compensation to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Figure 1, 2; Australian human rights commission should recommend/order to the government of Australia and/or Victoria legal aids to ensure the legal support and legal stipend. Applicant is international student/researcher, he had/has no money for going to international court/Australian court. Accordingly, applicant explained the whole matter different times, invested thousand and thousand of hours for convincing through different notices, reports, and letters; but the commission can not understand the approach of the applicant in English language. Accordingly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is ordering, recommending, and requesting to the office of Australian

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

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<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT</p>	<p>Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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human rights commission when Victoria legal aids(A. Hossain, 2023; M. A. Hossain, 2023c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b) is not approving the legal funds to ensure the legal support and safety to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. If Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should not get the legal recommendation, the function Australian human rights commission should be expelled in Australia/UN. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is communicating and replying this e-mail to the office of Australian human rights commission, but he is not getting salary and safety to survive in Australia and/or Bangladesh. If Australian human rights commission is not liable to satisfy the right duty in Australia, the commission should pay the compensation, the commission should face the judicial board of high court of Australia if commission has any judicial limitation to establish and understand the human rights in Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023bx).

4.3 Australian human rights commission should pay the legal consultancy charge of 5,000 USD to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain to satisfy the legal response on 20 October 2025

Figure 1, 2; the commission should not explain any judicial section to nullify the duties and responsibilities of human rights commission in Australia, if commission can not extend their helping hand if commission can not prove their official duty. Moreover, every legal act/legal claim can not be directly written to solve the judicial claim to register the judicial acts all over the world. Possibly, human rights commission in Australia should take administrative support of specialized lawyers in Australia to establish the duty of Australian human rights commission? If a person in Australia sees the criminal activities beside the Sydney Road in Melbourne, he/she should complain/call to '000', but the Australian human rights commission can not take the necessary action against the long-term life-threatening conspiracy but the commission is writing e-mail to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain on behalf of human rights commission. So, the commission should pay the compensation to satisfy the official duty. This is the judicial recommendation of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). The judicial/barristerial writing charge of this report is 5000 USD. Australian human rights commission should pay to the bank account of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain for the food cost and living cost support of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Bank account details: Md. Anowar Hossain, savings account no: 0178 12200003933, First security Islami bank PLC, Birulia Branch, Dhaka-(Routing No: 105260808). Mr/Ms Kate, Complaint Information Officer, National Information Services (incl Respect@Work), Investigation and Conciliation Service and/or office of Australian human rights commission should pay the judicial service charge of 5000 USD to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain(M. A. Hossain, 2023e; Hossain, 2025a). If the officer and supervisor are replying the e-mail on behalf of Mr. Hugh de

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia
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Kretser, President, Australian human rights commission; where is the personal secretary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at RMIT University in Australia since 2021-2022 (M. A. Hossain, 2023bx). Why should he write since 2021-2022? Why should he ask for the legal support and legal fund since 2021-2022? Who should take care the reason? Who is administering/leading the Australia? Who is controlling the supreme power of Australia? Who is controlling the supreme power of Australian human rights commission if the legal urge of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is failing and failing since 2021-2022?

4.4 Every international scholar should get honorary citizenship of Australia/free of cost citizenship of Australia for his/her contribution to the government of Australia.

Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should get honorary citizenship of Australia for his contribution to the government of Australia for taking risk to complaint to eliminate crimes and criminal in Australia (M. A. Hossain, 2023bx). He is also attaching his full contribution to the government of Australia to establish the scholar rights in Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also long-term campaigning to establish the human rights, professional rights, the rights of high-profile professionals, politicians, and ethical communities (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023bx; Hossain, 2025a). Every good quality person/every professor should have rights to reside in Australia in any place in Australia. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have rights to reside in Australia, if the criminals are also residing in Australia.

5 Acknowledgement

Sole author, Chief Director, PhD Research; Chief Director, Textile, Defence, and Law Research centre, RMIT; Chief Researcher, Textile, Color, and Material Research Centre, RMIT <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287> Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Hossain, Islam, et al., 2018; A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2019; A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2018; Hossain, Samanta, Bhaumik, et al., 2018; Hossain, Samanta, NS, et al., 2018; A. Hossain et al., 2019; Hossain, 2009, 2010b, 2010c, 2015a, 2019a, 2019c, 2019d; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; M. A. Hossain, 2023ap; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2019) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (M. A. Hossain, 2023aj, 2023am, 2023bj, 2023ci, 2023cj) (Anowar Hossain, 2016; A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2023; Hossain, 17 May 2023, 2010a, 2015b, 2015c, 2018, 2019b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; M. A. Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f, 2023h, 2023i, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o, 2023p,

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2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023y, 2023z, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ae, 2023af, 2023ag, 2023ah, 2023ai, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ao, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023ar, 2023as, 2023at, 2023au, 2023av, 2023aw, 2023ax, 2023ay, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bl, 2023bm, 2023bn; M. A. Hossain, 2023a; M. A. Hossain, 2023bo, 2023bp, 2023bq, 2023br, 2023bs, 2023bt; M. A. Hossain, 2023b; M. A. Hossain, 2023bu, 2023bv, 2023bw; M. A. Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e; M. A. Hossain, 2023by, 2023bz, 2023ca, 2023cb, 2023cc, 2023cd, 2023ce; M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; M. A. Hossain, 2023cf, 2023cg, 2023ch, 2023ci, 2023cj, 2023ck, 2023cl; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g, 2024h, 2024i, 2024j, 2024k, 2024l, 2024m, 2024n, 2024o, 2024p, 2024q, 2024r, 2024s, 2024t, 2024u, 2024v, 2024w, 2024y, 2024z; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024aa; Hossain, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d, 2025e, 2025f, 2025g, 2025h, 2025i; Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, 2025); name of father: late Dr. Md. Abdur Rashid, medical practitioner; permanent residence (PR): village: Purbo Nuthurchar, post office: K. Mohonpur (1990), police station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia (PR by birth); nationality, national ID, passport and birth registration number: Bangladeshi, 19862692620993890, A15988852/EE0444946/AF3831770, 003236; PhD (Doctor of Philosophy) application ID: 2612540, PhD student ID: 3820066, program name: DR213, PhD (fashion and textiles), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; lecturer on textile engineering (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh acknowledges RMIT University and the Australian government for funding through research training program (RTP) stipend scholarship, 2020-2025. Author, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>) also acknowledges ‘Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang’ (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7300-9271>) and ‘Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks’ (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3790-5148>) for their PhD supervision works at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

6 Proposal of legal funding for high court hearing in Australia and/or international court

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is asking and searching legal fund to the Victoria legal aids (A. Hossain, 2023), authority of any country, human rights commission of any country, United Nations, universities, research organizations, relevant authority of Australia and/or any government(M. A. Hossain, 2023bx).

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

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7 Limitations of writing this report to the president of Australian human rights commission

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) had food crisis, living cost crisis, and safety crisis to write this report for the legal costs and legal support for the legal claim in Australian court and/or international court when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was a valid member/citizen of association/country of Bangladesh (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023bw, 2023bx; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k, 2024x; Hossain, 2025g, 2025h).

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8 Author contribution and authorship status of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

The author has contribution in conceptualization, visualization, resource, self-supervision, funding acquisition, project administration, research communications, planning and prediction, analysis, writing the original draft, manuscript editing, and publication process. The scholarship or funder has no scholarly role of the design of research, research idea or visualization, research and innovation, drafting of manuscript, editing of manuscript, and publication of manuscript.

9 Declaration of conflicting interests

The author declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

10 Funding

The author received no financial support for the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

11 Data availability

All data generated during the coalescing of this article are included, attached and briefly cited in reference list.

12 Notes of exemption in the research of applied law and criminology for zero crime approach for the peace of mankind

The criminal/criminals/crime/crimes/people/peoples is/are international. The crime history is original and practical in PhD and Postdoc journey of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at RMIT

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

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University, Australia. In the research of applied law and criminology, the relevant human assessment, names, case studies, and organizations have been cited and implemented

- ✓ to establish the legal rights and human rights to the researchers/PhD scholars/professors/scientists.
- ✓ to protect the data information of crimes and criminals for the international category judicial assessment.
- ✓ to show the practical evidence of crime and criminals.
- ✓ to protect the peoples to ensure human defence and human peace in international platform.
- ✓ to ensure the safety of relevant peoples and/or organizations and/or professor community and/or researcher community and/or RMIT University, Australia.
- ✓ to notify crime courts, judges, review boards, judicial board, human rights, United Nations, and relevant international communities.
- ✓ to continue research and development.
- ✓ to circulate the outcomes of academic research.
- ✓ to approach zero crime for the peace of mankind.

13 Legal authorization and signing

Your honour, please pardon me
 Best regards for your excellency

 24 October 2025

(Md. Anowar Hossain)

Signature

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.); Postdoc & PhD in Applied Law; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, and BSc Engineering in Textile Technology

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTEch
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
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Chief Director and Founder; Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre; RMIT University, Australia.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

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14 Research address and contact

512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

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15 Permanent address and contact

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, Post Office: K. Mohonpur (1990), Police Station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh (by birth)

16 Evidences of e-mail communication

16.1.1RE: Your contact with AHRC [SEC=OFFICIAL]

Info Service

infoservice@humanrights.gov.au

To: me · Tue, Oct 14 at 4:50 AM

Message Body

Dear Md. Anowar Hossain,

I refer to your email about RMIT University, addressed to Mr Hugh de Krestler, President of the Australian Human Rights Commission (the Commission). The matter has been referred to the Investigation and Conciliation Service for response, which manages the Commission's complaint handling function.

What we do

For your information, the Commission has the power to investigate and conciliate complaints about:

- discrimination because of a person's race, sex, gender identity, sexual orientation, intersex status, pregnancy, marital or relationship status, age or disability as well as sexual harassment and sex based harassment in specific areas of public life, such as, employment, education and the provision of goods and services;
- being exposed to a hostile workplace environment because of their sex;
- racial hatred that takes place in public;

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 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh);
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD
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 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25: School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

- discrimination in employment because of a person's criminal record, trade union activity, religion, political opinion or social origin; or
- breaches of human rights by the Commonwealth of Australia.

Your concerns

In your email, you wrote:

- Nobody should have right to cease the rights of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.
- Nobody should cease the money/salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.
- He also needs living and food allowance.
- RMIT should not cease single dollar from the pocket of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.
- Nobody should plan to kill the researcher.
- Nobody should harass the merit growth of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.

Based on the email alone, it is not clear how your concerns could arguably be covered by the Commission's complaint handling jurisdiction as set out above.

In your correspondence, you also attached a 259 page document. I'm sorry, but we are not in a position to review this document due to its length and our significant resource constraints. If you believe that these are concerns that the Commission can consider, it is open for you to provide a more succinct version, covering the main points and limited to 20 pages in length.

Free legal help is available

You may wish to seek legal advice about your current options. For free legal advice, you can contact:

- [Legal Aid of VIC](#)
- [Community legal centre](#)

Should you have any further queries or wish to provide clarification, please advise by return email or call our National Information Service on 1300 656 419.

Kind regards,

Kate (she/her)

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia to United Nations; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 24 October 2025.

Complaint Information Officer
National Information Services (incl Respect@Work)
Investigation and Conciliation Service

Please note my working days are Monday, Tuesday and Friday

Page | 16

Australian Human Rights Commission

GPO Box 5218, Sydney NSW 2001

T National Information Services 1300 656 419 (Monday to Friday between 10.00am and 4.00pm AEST)

E infoservice@humanrights.gov.au **W** www.humanrights.gov.au

Anowar Hossain

To: Info · Thu, Oct 16 at 4:54 PM

Message Body

Kate (she/her)

Complaint Information Officer

National Information Services (incl Respect@Work)

Investigation and Conciliation Service

Dear Sir,

Australian human rights commission may recommend to Victoria legal aids to approve legal stipend or a full funding legal support to the international applicant. Due to having the communication of long-term duration, the evidence of communication and page numbers are higher. Please consider the short summery of the victim impact statement.

Reporting to Victoria Legal Aid, Australia for the grant of legal assistance for ethical defending for the peace in PhD education against conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD School. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10207100>

A follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

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threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18369.83044>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17231359>

Victim impact statement of Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, cancellation of PhD enrolment ID: 3820066 under the conspiracy of killing PhD candidate, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Bangladeshi (by birth)

Purpose of reporting to the relevant court in Australia

- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking PhD enrolment with scholarship funding
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain asked his personal safety to Vice chancellor, RMIT University but Vice chancellor gave him executive suspension.
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain asked his personal protection from Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye on 24 January 2022 but Vice chancellor gave him executive suspension
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking legal remedy for life protection in home and abroad against threatening of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking legal remedy against the harassment of PhD research funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking legal remedy of life time health impact
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking life time personal protection against Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye and his associates in home and abroad
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking life-long protection from life-threatening and trafficking activities of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking withdrawn of unethical PhD suspension, PhD enrolment and PhD degree without any artificial harassment when he has PhD effort of full time since February 2020 to still now

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia to United Nations; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 24 October 2025.

- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain seeking a compensation of artificial PhD harassment from December 2021 to still now
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is seeking and ensuring of non-paid PhD scholarship to PhD candidate
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain asked for lawyer support from RMIT University on 24 January 2022 but he got unexpected and unethical executive suspension on 6 July 2022
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain asked for safety support from RMIT University on 24 January 2022 but he got unexpected and unethical executive suspension on 6 July 2022
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain invested a lot of Australian Dollar for his PhD research and he submitted his PhD thesis through second milestone, he should get PhD degree without harassment without life-threatening.
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had allegation against Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye when Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron was silent when Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron was holding an administrative position of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had allegation against Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye when Dr. Andrea Eckersley was silent when Dr. Andrea Eckersley was holding an administrative position of HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had allegation against Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye when Dr. Scott Mayson was silent when Dr. Scott Mayson was holding an administrative position of Associate Dean (Research & Innovation), School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had allegation against Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye when Professor (Dr) Calum Drummond was silent when Professor (Dr) Calum Drummond was holding an administrative position of Deputy Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
- ✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had allegation against Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye when Professor (Dr) Lijing Wang was silent when Professor (Dr) Lijing Wang was holding Senior Supervisor position of PhD candidate, RMIT University

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh); MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁵ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT</p>	<p>Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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✓ Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had allegation against Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye when Professor (Dr) Robert Shanks was silent when Professor (Dr) Robert Shanks was holding associate supervisor position of PhD candidate, RMIT University

✓ Both Professor (Dr) Lijing Wang & Professor (Dr) Robert Shanks indirectly recommended and forwarded me to Professor (Dr) Rajiv Padhye when I officially notified conspiracy of life threatening against Professor Rajiv Padhye when I officially notified conspiracy of life threatening to the whole community of RMIT University.

✓ Dr. Abdur Rahman and Dr. Abu Shaïd also recommended for going to Professor (Dr) Rajiv Padhye. Dr. Abdur Rahman threatened me against the decision of Australian Government RTP stipend scholarship. Dr. Abdur Rahman assessed and commented about higher secondary certificate of Applicant, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Dr. Abdur Rahman didn't take any permission from the government of Australia and Government of Bangladesh.

✓ Dr. Saniyat Islam, Former PhD student of Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye was not happy when applicant came to PhD school regularly for doing PhD research to satisfy his PhD requirement, Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang. Dr. Saniyat Islam showed threatening attitude to applicant, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.

✓ My PhD degree is being threatened now along with the conspiracy of life-threatening at PhD school. I hardly worked for PhD degree/PhD research since February 2020 to June 2022 under RTP stipend scholarship, 31260AUD/year, 2605AUD/month. My actual salary should be minimum 240000USD/year, 20000USD/month under Australian Compliance.

✓ Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-invested around 1000000 USD (in words ten lakh USD) for his full time PhD education from February 2020 to August 2023.

PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8254280>

PhD degree is my achievement and my investment. Nobody should cease my legal achievement through threatening and conspiracy of life threatening. Applicant is seeking support through Australian Government Lawyer. The matter was a long-term discussion with RMIT university. Presently life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue is converted to the cancellation of PhD enrolment. Presently, applicant is residing in Bangladesh. Please if office of legal aid can advise to applicant if there is any option of online hearing in front of judge of any relevant court; by this way if applicant can protect his life, his PhD degree and his PhD funding. Applicant have no money for coming to Melbourne and residing to face judge court in Melbourne.

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

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Applicant was fully dependent on the administration of RMIT University but applicant is long term sufferer now since January 2022 and applicant has no way to get Australian court and policing support directly. Otherwise, Applicant is seeking right funding for residing in Australia under policing safety.

This email has a pdf file of nine pages of full letter.

*Your Honour; Please Pardon Me
Best Regards for your excellency*

**Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist
PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing
Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)**

**Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry
Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia
Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering
City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore
Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering
Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong
Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)**

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com, engranowar06@gmail.com, +8801788396264

Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Enqr-Md-Hossain>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

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www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Info Service

To: me · Mon, Oct 20 at 7:13 AM

Message Body

Dear Mr Hossein,

I refer to your recent email to the Australian Human Rights Commission (the Commission).

I understand the seriousness of the concerns you have raised and can appreciate how distressing these events have been for you and other families and I am deeply sorry for that.

Without at all seeking to dismiss or diminish your concerns, unfortunately, from the information you have provided it does not appear that the Commission's Investigation and Conciliation Section can help you with this matter because it does not appear that the issues you have raised fall under our complaint handling jurisdiction.

I wish to advise that [section 11\(1\)\(f\)](#) of the [Australian Human Rights Commission Act 1986](#) (Cth) (the **AHRCA**) says that the Commission can inquire into an alleged 'act' or 'practice' that may be inconsistent with, or contrary to, any human right. The terms 'act' and 'practice' are defined in section 3 of the AHRCA as an act or practice by, or on behalf of, the Commonwealth or a Commonwealth authority. Therefore, the Commission can only consider complaints about alleged breaches of human rights where the alleged act or practice was done by, or on behalf of, the Commonwealth or a Commonwealth authority. The Commission has no power to inquire into alleged breaches of human rights by state government departments or agencies, private companies and entities and/or individuals.

Notwithstanding the above, the Commission's powers in relation to complaints about a breach of human rights are very limited. The Commission can, where appropriate, assist parties to try to resolve a complaint by conciliation. However, if the complaint is not able to be resolved through the Commission's conciliation process and the President finds that there has been a breach of human rights, the President can prepare a report on the complaint, including recommendations, for the Federal Attorney-General. In that report, the President can recommend an outcome, but the President cannot order the respondent to provide a remedy – it is open for the respondent not to take on the recommendation and the Commission is not able to enforce compliance of it.

Why the Commission is not able to assist

Under the Commission's human rights jurisdiction we can inquire into any act or practice by or on behalf of the Commonwealth that may be

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

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inconsistent with a human right contained in an international human rights instrument scheduled to or declared under the *Australian Human Rights Commission Act 1986 (Cth)*, such as the *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights* and the *Convention on the Rights of the Child*. There is nothing in the information that you have provided that would suggest that the Commonwealth of Australia has engaged in an act or practice in relation to you that would bring this matter into the Commission's human rights complaint handling jurisdiction.

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Please also note this Commission is primarily a dispute resolution body and we do not function like a court. We do not have the power to order a remedy or to take particular action, such as issuing apology, paying financial compensation etc. and we do not have the power to issue any sanctions, penalties or otherwise take any disciplinary action against other departments, agencies, organisations and/or individuals.

Unfortunately, whilst the Commission acknowledges that the issues you have raised are of significant concern to you, the issues you have raised do not appear to be within our jurisdiction. I appreciate that you may be disappointed by the limited jurisdiction of the Commission.

I can only suggest that you seek legal advice, if you have not done so already.

We wish you all the best.

Kind regards,

Andrew

Supervisor, National Information Services (incl. Respect@Work)
Investigation and Conciliation Service

Australian Human Rights Commission

GPO Box 5218, Sydney NSW 2001

T National Information Service 1300 656 419 (Monday to Friday between 10.00am and 4.00pm AEDT)

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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 24 October 2025.

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18 If necessary, please visit online profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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19 Professional excellency of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, engr.anowar@yahoo.com.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>

Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>

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Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com.

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research.

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11516770>

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>

Invitation of law researchers in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.

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Invitation of legal client for legal service to individual and/or organization.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13073.70249>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16990186>

Invitation of researchers in textile engineering in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17215.57765>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16960861> Page | 45

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Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University,

Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

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 right adjustment of my designation under consideration of my Curriculum Vitae (CV),*

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Visible-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds (Global Summit on
 Chemical Engineering and Catalysis (ISTRCEC 2023), accepted on 20 March 2023;

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International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Accepted on 28 March

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844652>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ak). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating*

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Second milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy [Fashion and Textiles,

RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056,

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illumination, PhD student: 3820066, First milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of

philosophy [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick

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Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia to United Nations; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 24 October 2025.

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Nobel Nominée Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
 Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)³
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁴
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre: RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre: RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre: RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre: CU, BD
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre: JU, BD
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech: University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre: CU, India
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India: Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25: School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Industry, engr.anowar@yahoo.com. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>;
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Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia to United Nations; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 24 October 2025.

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28176.28165>

<p>Nobel Nominer Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT</p>	<p>Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Hossain, M. A. (2023bm). *PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747607>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bn). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking necessary action by the Australian crime commission act (ACC), 2002; 7A, 7C and/or relevant act of criminal investigation in PhD school.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26327.04002>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10116196>

Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking free of cost legal action to high court of Australia and/or fully funded PhD Scholarship for every cost of high court of Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27057.76642>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10182345>

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Hossain, M. A. (2023bp). *Power Point Presentation on Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds (School of fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022, Issue.*

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16258214>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bs). Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. *Scholarly Community Encyclopedia.* <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49098>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bt). *Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist.*

<https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49098>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34177.43368>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10208384>

Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Bangladeshi Passport No: EE0444946; Bangladeshi Address: Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh is reporting life-*

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia to United Nations; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 24 October 2025.

threatening conspiracy to Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Australian High Commissioner to Bangladesh located at 184 Gulshan Avenue, Gulshan, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28153.24164>;

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Hossain, M. A. (2023bu). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is begging to Mr. António Guterres, the Secretary General of United Nations to stop the conflict between Gaza & Israel.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25967.41129>;

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Hossain, M. A. (2023bv). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13240.32001>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360586>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bw). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12742364>

Hossain, M. A. (2023c). *Reporting and filing to High Court of Australia for court hearing & court writ of life-threatening conspiracy to kill PhD researcher and artificial killing conspiracy of PhD dream of a PhD scholar in a prestigious platform of PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20689.30567>;

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Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Reporting to Honorable Minister, Department of Home Affairs, Australia and delegates for activation and extension of VISA of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University until the final order of Australian Supreme Court, Australian human rights commission and chief authorities of Australian Government relates to PhD harassment and conspiracy of life-threatening of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.17927>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195451>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 24 October 2025.

Nobel Nominée Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25: School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Hossain, M. A. (2023by). *Reporting to Tertiary Education Quality & Standards Agency of Australian Government for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship.* . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bz). *Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship.* . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8315574>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ca). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Year 2006-2010 (academic), 2017-2019 (professional).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19275.98087>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286941>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cb). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India, 2013-2015.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12565.09440>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15068327>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cc). *Self-declared certificate on PhD (Fashion & Textiles)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30457.65123>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10978165>

Self-declared certificate on Professor (Textile Engineering), (2023cd).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36591.82084>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275164>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ce). *Self-declared certificate on Scientist (Camouflage Physics)* (Australia Patent No. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13103.71848>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275143>

Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>

Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cf). *A short summery and evidences of Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14593.43368>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12722555>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cg). Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM) incorporated with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials for special workers and extreme weather conditions; Accepted in Advanced Material Research (2019-2020). *School of Fashions and Textiles, RMIT University, Victoria 3056, Australia* (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8112357>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32289.79204>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ch). *Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ci). Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums. *MRS Communications* <https://doi.org/10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cj). UV–Visible–NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection.

Scientific Reports. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31725-2>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 24 October 2025.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre: RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre: RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre: RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre: CU, BD
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre: JU, BD
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech: University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India: Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25: School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ck). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01).*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cl). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02).*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/0WXVkgicfKg>

Hossain, M. A. (2024a). Advancement in UV-Vis-IR camouflage Textiles for concealment of defense surveillance against multidimensional combat background. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Engineering.* <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40712-024-00182-8>;

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17601.12648>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14282484>

Hossain, M. A. (2024b). *Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14776.72967>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>

Hossain, M. A. (2024c). *Coalesced the syllabus and course structures in textile engineering and relevant courses in the eighteen years duration academic and professional journey of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist from 2006 to 2024.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21803.66082>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13888294>

Hossain, M. A. (2024d). *Cyber securities for protection of cyber-crimes.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14367.98729>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841349>

Hossain, M. A. (2024e). *A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964382>

Hossain, M. A. (2024f). *Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of “Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist” on “Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds”* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia to United Nations; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 24 October 2025.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36270.32328;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13182515>

Hossain, M. A. (2024g). *Letter to Nobel committee for Nobel prize in camouflage physics.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36807.51367;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842435>

Hossain, M. A. (2024h). *Letter to Nobel Committee for Nobel Prize in Peace.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35129.79208;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842361>

Hossain, M. A. (2024i). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching research fund for surviving in research profession and self-learning.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22732.42888;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13997939>

Hossain, M. A. (2024j). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699107>

Hossain, M. A. (2024k). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>

Hossain, M. A. (2024l). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of 'free of cost google drive (2TB) access' to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28761.94568;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13994976>

Hossain, M. A. (2024m). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is self-nominating for 'global excellence award' at Functional Textiles and Clothing (FTC), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India under the category of 'Leadership in Research' and/or 'Emerging Innovator' under the invitation of FTC team, IIT, Delhi, India.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36325.61929;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14213757>

Hossain, M. A. (2024n). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is asking an exemption of visa fees for the 'Australian global talent*

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 24 October 2025.

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), M.Tech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT</p>	<p>Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Vyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25: School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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*permanent residence visa (subclass 858) under the Australian migration act 45C (c), 1958 and 500.211,1994. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25869.14560>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12754106>*

Hossain, M. A. (2024o). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Hossain, M. A. (2024p). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>

Hossain, M. A. (2024q). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Calcutta for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20869.15843>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842021>

Hossain, M. A. (2024r). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Dhaka for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia*

(engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36388.08325>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841964>

Hossain, M. A. (2024s). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is searching a good-looking lady for his marriage, a requirement of RMIT PhD school.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13112.97282>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747830>

Hossain, M. A. (2024t). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16628548>

Hossain, M. A. (2024u). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>

Barrister Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia to United Nations; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 24 October 2025.

- Hossain, M. A. (2024v). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an international standard University.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814275>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024w). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>
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